

(iii) except in case of **2b** and **2d**, the hydroxyl protons could not be traced.

Compound 2a: M.p. 161-62° (ethanol) (lit¹. 162°) (Found: C, 74.70; H, 5.85. C₁₅H₁₄O₃ requires: C, 74.38; H, 5.79%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 440 (OH) and 1 740 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (80 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.46-2.85 (10H, m, Ar), 6.64 and 6.79 (1H, d each, *J* 11 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2b: M.p. 178-79 (ethanol) (Found: C, 74.20; H, 6.24. C₁₅H₁₆O₃ requires: C, 75.0; H, 6.25%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 419 (OH) and 1 724 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (80 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.35-3.02 (9H, m, Ar), 5.78 (1H, s, OH), 6.70 and 6.86 (1H, d each, *J* 13.5 Hz, benzylic), 7.79 (3H, s, CH₃).

Compound 2c: M.p. 203-05° (ethanol) (Found: C, 64.61; H, 4.62. C₁₅H₁₃O₃Cl requires: C, 65.10; H, 4.70%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 424 (OH) and 1 724 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (80 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.47-2.81 (9H, m, Ar), 6.64 and 6.77 (1H, d each, *J* 11 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2d: M.p. 136-38° (ethanol) (Found: C, 65.09; H, 4.71. C₁₅H₁₃O₃Cl requires: C, 65.10; H, 4.70%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 450 (OH) and 1 719 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 2.3-3.0 (9H, m, Ar), 4.5-5.2 (OH), 6.2 and 6.4 (1H, d each, *J* 15 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2e: M.p. 194-95° (ethanol) (Found: C, 65.24; H, 4.82. C₁₅H₁₃O₃Cl requires: C, 65.10; H, 4.70%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 414 (OH) and 1 727 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.38 and 2.64 (2H, d each, *J* 8.6 Hz, *p*-disubst. Ar), 2.85 (5H, s, Ar), 6.59 and 6.78 (1H, d each, *J* 14.6 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2f: M.p. 129-30° (ethanol) (Found: C, 64.40; H, 4.62. C₁₅H₁₃O₃Cl requires: C, 65.10; H, 4.70%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 424 (OH) and 1 724 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.41-2.91 (9H, m, Ar), 6.57 and 6.82 (1H, d each, *J* 13.5 Hz, benzylic).

Compound 2g: M.p. 175-76° (ethanol) (Found: C, 66.30; H, 5.17. C₁₅H₁₅O₃Cl requires: C, 66.10; H, 5.16%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 412 (OH) and 1 723 cm⁻¹ (C=O); τ (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆) 2.57 and 2.64 (2H, d each, *J* 8.5 Hz, *p*-disubst. Ar), 2.96-3.17 (4H, m, Ar), 6.66 and 6.88 (1H, d each, *J* 13.2 Hz, benzylic) and 7.51 (s, OH), 7.8 (3H, s, CH₃).

All the ir spectra were measured in KBr pellets. TMS was used as internal standard in all nmr measurements.

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Polymer supported Hydroxycoumarin Anion. Convenient Method for *O*-Alkylation of Hydroxycoumarin

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THE reagents supported on insoluble polymers have found wide applications during the last decade in various fields, particularly in organic synthesis¹. In continuation of our work on polymer supported reactions² and in view of the importance of *O*-alkylated hydroxycoumarins as a basic compound in drug industry³, a simple and efficient method is now reported for the *O*-alkylation of hydroxycoumarins. The use of anion-exchange resin for *O*-alkylation of hydroxycoumarins which combine the advantage of solid phase synthesis and anionic activation. Owing to the effectiveness of this system, extraordinarily mild reaction conditions can be employed.

Experimental

Alkyl halide in methanol was reacted with hydroxy coumarin anion bound to the ion-exchange resin. Alkylation was complete within 6 to 10 h at room temperature giving quantitative yields of products in essentially pure form. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Amberlyst A-26 hydroxycoumarin anion: Commercial strongly basic anion-exchange resin in the

TABLE 1—O-ALKYLATION OF HYDROXYCOUMARINS WITH ALKYL HALIDES AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Anion	Alkylating agent	Reaction time h	Yield %	M.p.* °C
	CH ₃ I	6	99	157 (159) ^a
	C ₆ H ₅ I	8	96	95
	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ Cl	10	99	85
	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ Br	10	100	102
	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH ₂ I	10	96	82
	CH ₃ I	6	99	124 (124) ^b
	C ₆ H ₅ I	8	96	185 (186) ^b
	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ Cl	8	90	110
	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ Br	6	96	100
	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH ₂ I	10	90	88
	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ I	10	95	92

*Literature value in parenthesis. ^aJ. M. KAUFFMAN, *Appl. Opt.*, 1981, 19, 3491. ^bRef. 3.

chloride form (Amberlyst A-26) packed in a column was washed with aqueous 5% sodium salt of hydroxycoumarin until complete removal of chloride ion. The resin was then successively washed with water, ethanol and benzene and finally dried *in vacuo* at 50° over phosphorus pentoxide for 12 h. The exchange capacity was determined by passing aqueous 1 N sodium chloride (100 ml) through the resin (0.3 g) in a column. The amount of hydroxycoumarin anion in the eluent was titrated with 0.01 N hydrochloric acid using methyl orange as indicator. The product I contains 1.2 mmol hydroxycoumarin per g of resin and product II 1.4 mmol hydroxy coumarin per g of resin.

Alkylation procedure: Amberlyst A-26 hydroxycoumarin anion form (containing 5 mmol hydroxycoumarin) in methanol (15 ml) was stirred with an appropriate alkyl halide (5.01 mmol) in a stoppered flask. After completion of the reaction the resin was removed by filtration and washed with methanol. The distillation of the solvent furnished corresponding alkylated product in quantitative yield in essentially pure form. The products were characterised by comparison of the melting points, ir and nmr spectra with those of authentic samples. The resin used may, in all cases, be easily regenerated by washing with hydrochloric acid.

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Substituted 1,8-Naphthyridines. Part-III. Synthesis and Biological Activity of some 1,8-Naphthyridine Derivatives

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1,8-Naphthyridine derivatives have been reported to possess antibacterial¹⁻⁶ and antimalarial^{7,8} activities. Nalidixic acid (1-ethyl-3-carboxy-7-methyl-1,8-naphthyridin-4-one) has been found to be particularly effective against gram-negative bacteria⁹ found in chronic urinary tract infections. Various 2,3-disubstituted-1,8-naphthyridines have been found to be associated with diuretic activity^{10,11}. In view of this, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise a series of unreported 2-substituted-1,8-naphthyridines and test them for their biological activity.

The present communication deals with a one-step synthesis of 2-aryl-1,8-naphthyridines (2), involving the Friedlander condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) with arylmethyl ketones in glacial acetic acid with a trace of concentrated sulphuric acid. The same reaction was also carried out in alcohol medium with a few drops of piperidine. The yields are better under acid conditions. The structures of these compounds have been established by elemental analyses and spectral data. The ir spectra of 2 showed bands at 1 600 (C=N), 1 590, 1 540, 1 420, 1 300 and 800 cm⁻¹. The mass spectra of 2 exhibited strong molecular ion peaks consistent with their elemental analyses. The mass spectra of 2-*p*-chloro-

phenyl and 2-nitrophenyl 2 showed strong M^+ peaks at m/z 240 and 251, respectively. The mass spectrum of 2 (R = *p*-Cl.C₆H₄) showed strong M^+ peaks at m/z 240 (M^+ , 84%), 239 ($M^+ - H$, 3%), 205 ($M^+ - Cl$, 10), 204 ($M^+ - Cl - H$, 17), 179 ($M^+ - Cl - C_6H_5$, 10), 178 ($M^+ - Cl - HCN$, 12), 177 (204 - HCN, 17), 152 (179 - HCN, 9), 151 (12), 103 (9), 102 (25), 77 (11),

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